

Development of 3D GIS-Based Model for Management of Urban Solid Waste in Aba Metropolis Abia State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to develop 3D GIS-Based Model for Management of Urban Solid Waste in Aba Metropolis Abia State Nigeria. The objectives include to identify and collect waste disposal point within Aba Metropolis using Geo-spatial technology, to create the database of features (buildings, road, solid waste disposal point), to develop a digital 3D GIS-Based model for management of urban Solid waste in Aba Metropolis and to recommend the best solution based from the analysis obtained. The dataset included base map from Ministry of Lands and Survey, waste collection point data acquired using Handheld GPS and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV DJI Phantom 4) analysis in Agisoft and other Geo-spatial software, projected population density data from National Population. Data processing involved scanning, georeferencing, digitizing, superimposing or overlay of data from different data source in Arc Map. The results include 68063 buildings and 3682 roads digitized, location of twenty-eight (28) waste collection and three (3) waste disposal points with Geo-spatial technology, development of a 3D GIS based waste model of a disposal site with a Perimeter of 269.252m Area 4633.2 (m²) volume above 47503.9(m³) below 13.659 (m³) total 47490.3 (m³), another result from buffer analysis reveals 1125 and 7065 buildings housing people around collection and disposal point respectively are under waste risk especially along Aba River (waterside) as multi criteria analysis was further used to confirm waste hazard, vulnerability and risk. From the analysis there should be house to house collection of waste to enable government combat and control the discharge of waste within the urban area was recommended, this can be achieved successful with help of database creation in Geographic Information System especially a 3D model of waste, buildings, road as this will show reality of Aba and its environment. This will eventually help in improving the socio-economic life of the people for sustainability, improved living and good governance which is apt with the Un-habitat vision of 2030 agenda on sustainable environment and socio-economic development globally.

Keywords: Aba, Abia State, GIS, Solid Waste, Waste Management,

1 Introduction

Solid waste is any material that is discarded by being abandoned (thrown away) disposed of, burned, incinerated, or sham recycled which can be any garbage or refuse, sludge from a waste water treatment plant, water supply treatment plant or air pollution control facility and other discarded material, resulting from industrial, commercial, mining, and agricultural operations, and from community activities. Nearly everything we do leaves behind some kind of waste (US Environmental Protection Agency 2023). Meanwhile, waste as an end, an unused product of a useful element, spoiled item, useless and valueless items, debris, refuse junks and liquid waste etc., can be tangible and intangible (Chijioke 2016).

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US Environmental Protection Agency (2023) clarified further that solid waste is not limited to wastes that are physically solid; many are liquid, semi-solid, or contained gaseous material. Most inherently solid waste-like are some materials that pose a threat to human health and the environment examples include dioxin-containing wastes, a discarded military munition military, all ammunition products and components produced for or used by the U.S. Department of Defense (DOD) or U.S. Armed Services for national defense and security when abandoned, disposed of, burned, incinerated or treated prior to disposal, rendered non-recyclable or non-usable through deterioration or declared a waste by an authorized military official even it is used (that is fired or detonated) munitions so far it is collected for storage, recycling, treatment, or disposal

Nevertheless, Sonny *et al* (2022) defined Solid Waste Management (SWM) as an orderly approach to waste disposal which is concerned with the safe collection, transportation, and its treatment that's a combination of techniques of disposing of, collecting and recycling of solid waste. Effective management of waste is vital for maintaining a sustainable environment. In countries where illegal disposal of waste and pollution are rampant, waste management deal with deadly diseases such as cholera and malaria. Though, management of solid waste is a global issue facing most cities in the world; a major environmental problems across the global Chalkias and Lasaridi (2011); Tavares Zsigraiova and Semiao (2009) in Etibar, and Aytaj, (2023) elaborate further that collecting, treating and disposing of solid material is discarded because it has served its purpose or is no longer useful, its improper disposal create unsanitary conditions that can lead to pollution of the environment and to outbreaks of vector borne disease (rodents and insects). Thus, the tasks of solid-waste management present complex technical challenges, that pose a wide variety of administrative, economic, and social problems that must be managed and solved.

According to Jerry (2023) in ancient cities, wastes were thrown onto unpaved streets and roadways, where they were left to accumulate. It was not until 320 BCE in Athens that the first known law forbidding this practice was established. At that time a system for waste removal began to evolve in

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Greece and in the Greek-dominated cities of the eastern Mediterranean. A technological approach to solid-waste management began to develop in the latter part of the 19th century.

Proper waste management is an essential part of society's public and environmental health, so Aba as a commercial city in Abia state with a fast growing population and high population density need a proper sanitation and environmental laws, policies orientation to safe guard the environmental health of the citizen as the present method of waste collection by Abia State environmental protection agency (ASEPA) is no longer adequate this include large skip bins for commercial areas, housing estates, streets and public institutions. These skip bins serve as central collection points where smaller bins are emptied and are regularly collected by the agency (Egesi *et al* 2016). This method becomes impedance to road accessibility (Portharcourt road dumpsite), a source of pollution and hazard Ngwa Road, Obunku, Emelogu and 7up/Glass Fort by Ukwudara and Dubic dumpsite etc.

Then, 3D GIS as a system which analysis, processes, manages and presents information related to three-dimensional topics, an addition of a third dimension (z coordinate) to a two-dimensional (x and y coordinates) plane or feature to create a 3D though heavily influenced by 2D (two-dimensional) GIS, has its distinct characteristics. By combining a z-value into mapping, 3D GIS adds a new dimension to data collection and analysis; this includes terrain visualization, cityscape modeling, augmented reality and sophisticated spatial data analysis, the core components are 3D data capture, 3D visualization, and 3D modeling and management. Final, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) as a system that acquire, process, analyse model earth related data can provide the necessary data and present information to stakeholders, construction engineers, and consultants, planners a GIS model to illustrate two-dimensional (2D) drawings and three-dimensional (3D) models by sequentially connecting their components to the operations in the schedule to demonstrate construction details (SATPALDA, 2022). Therefore, data development of 3D GIS based model for management of solid waste in Aba will be a require tool for management of waste as this will enable the government to get the actual legal and illegal collecting point, and curtail hazard that solid waste bring to her citizen.

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Aim and objective

The study aimed at development of 3D GIS-Based model for management of urban Solid waste in Aba Metropolis Abia State Nigeria, with a view of providing a good framework to waste management in Aba Metropolis. This was achieved through the following objectives: To

1. Identify and collect data on the waste collection and disposal points in Aba Metropolis Abia state using Geo-spatial technology.
2. create the database of features (buildings, road, solid waste collection and disposal point) in Aba Metropolis.
3. develop a digital 3D GIS-Based 3D model for management of urban Solid waste in Aba Metropolis.
4. analyse the solid waste collection and disposal suitability pattern of Aba Metropolis using Geospatial software.

2 Study area

Aba Metropolis is located in Abia state south eastern region of Nigeria seen (figure 1a, 1b, 1c,1d and 1e) approximately latitudes 5° 25' 30" to 5°27' 30" north, and longitudes 7°19' 30" and 7° 22' 30" east. Aba Urban is made up of Aba North, Aba South, part of Osisioma, part of Obingwa, and part of Ugwunagbo, it is bounded to the north by Isiala Ngwa North to the south Ugwunagbo to the east with other part of Obingwa and Akwa Ibom state, while to the west of Imo state and remaining part of Osisioma.

3. Material and Methods

Different data set and sources were used in the modelling and analysis, Surveying and other Geospatial method of data capture was employed such as office Search Planning Field Reconnaissance etc however, the data was divided include primary and secondary date, while data source and type were summaries in table 3.1

Primary Data Acquisition

These consist of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) data capture used for the disposal site for 3D GIS-Based model, Global Positioning system (GPS) used for waste collection point, personal observation and Ground truthing for the existing dump site and refuse collection

Secondary Data Acquisition

Quickbird 2018 (0.5m Resolution) updated Google Earth 2023 and Landsat ETM8+ (32m Resolution) used for supervise classification to know the general land use of Aba metropolis. The data is summarized in table 3.1

Table 3.1 Data types and sources

S/N	Data Types	Identification	Scale/ Resolution	Year	Sources	Format
1	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV DJI Phantom 4)	Aba Metropolis		2023	Field Work	Digital
2	Satellite image (Quickbird)	Aba Metropolis	0.5 meters	2018	Geo Eye Imagery Collection System Inc. US Government	Digital
3	Landsat ETM8+	Aba Metropolis	32 meters	2019	USGS	Digital
4	Basemap (Political map and Administration)	Aba Metropolis	1:250,000	1991	Ministry of Lands, Survey and Urban planning Umuahia	Analogue
4	Ground truthing	Identification of waste Bin and site Aba Metropolis		2023	Field Work	Digital
5	Population data	Projected Population and its Density of Aba Metropolis		2022	National population Commission	Analogue

4. Discussion of Result

The study reveal twenty eight (28) waste collection and three (3) waste disposal site figure 4.1 also digitized map and database of Aba urban including roads, building, river, railway and waste collection and disposal site in figure 4.3 table 4.1a and table 4.1b which comprises the whole of Aba North, Aba

South, part of Osisioma, Obingwa and Ugwunagbo, with 68063 buildings 3682 roads were digitized, many major roads cut across each LGA but the major recognise road in the project is PH-ASA-Aba Owerri Road where majority of the collection point were located. The figure 4.2 show the land use pattern of Aba Metropolis indicating 95% built up area, indicating no area within the metropolis is suitable for waste disposal

Figure 4.1 Aba Metropolis showing Dump Collection and Disposal points and Roads

Table 4.1a Digital Database of the Dump Collection Point

Attributes of Dump Collection Point

FID	Shape *	Easting	Northings	Height	Location_N	Date
0	Point ZM	315268.837	569126.366	88.2	Osisioma	Apr-23
1	Point ZM	317523.083	567888.602	87.2	Union Bank	Apr-23
2	Point ZM	319190.752	564940.217	82.7	Park	Apr-23
3	Point ZM	318119.096	567258.214	76.5	Umungasi	Apr-23
4	Point ZM	316894.932	568449.413	88.3	Anglican	Apr-23
5	Point ZM	322357	565127	0	Opobo Junction	May-23
6	Point ZM	319280	564842	0	Asa Road beside UBA	May-23
7	Point ZM	318590	564009	0	Asa By Cemetery	May-23
8	Point ZM	322162	567115	72	Along Obikabia Metrological Station	Jun-23
9	Point ZM	320788	567618	0	7 UP near Brittian Stars	Jun-23
10	Point ZM	324581	566876	0	Osusu Amaukwa no bucket	Jun-23
11	Point ZM	317888.426	563771.887	58.3	58 Portharcourt Rd	Aug-23
12	Point ZM	317326.5333	563522.663	48	Urta Road	Aug-23
13	Point ZM	314660.952	562273.634	53.2	Uratta Junction	Aug-23
14	Point ZM	314677.255	563216.892	61.6	Old Express to Arriaria	Aug-23
15	Point ZM	314662.422	563554.771	63	Opposite Liquid Bulk Filling Station	Aug-23
16	Point ZM	314631.439	564434.012	58	Ariaria junction	Aug-23
17	Point ZM	315821.207	565477.684	60.68	Ariaria Main Market	Aug-23
18	Point ZM	319987.345	565550.809	53	Geogres	Sep-23
19	Point ZM	319979.606	563686.269	60	Ngwa	Sep-23
20	Point ZM	321438.29	563860.19	27	Ngwa Emelogu	Sep-23
21	Point ZM	320207.11	567708.49	55	7up	Sep-23
22	Point ZM	320709.461	566702.683	61	7up by SDA	Sep-23
23	Point ZM	319898.96	564316.71	61	New Market	Sep-23
24	Point ZM	315871.72	565429.56	59	Ariaria Gate	Sep-23
25	Point ZM	314642.1	564685.85	55	Ariariaby Express	Sep-23
26	Point ZM	320448.941	565702.853	0	New Umuahia Rd by Waterside	Sep-23
27	Point ZM	322233.667	565485.663	0	Opobo Junction	
28	Point ZM	318999.016	564877.486	0	Asa Road beside UBA	
29	Point ZM	0	0	0		
30	Point ZM	0	0	0		
31	Point ZM	0	0	0		

Record: 1 | Show: All Selected | Records (0 out of 32 Selected) | Options

Table 4.1b Digital Database of the Dump Disposal Point

Attributes of Dump Disposal Point

FID	Shape *	Id	Name
0	Polygon	0	Ngwa Emelogu dump site
1	Polygon	0	7up Glass dump site
2	Polygon	0	World Bank Dump site

Figure 4.2 Supervise Classification of the study area

Figure 4.3 Aba Metropolis showing roads, buildings railway River

Development 3D GIS Based Model of Aba Metropolis and 2D imagery

From 4.4a to figure 4.4j showed the development of 3D GIS-Based Model Processing Steps using Agisoft Metashape Professional (World Bank Dump site) from figure 4.4 k to figure 4.4r showed 3D scene screen shot in different view while figure 4.4s showed 2D of the same dump site

Figure 4.4a Add Photos 3D GIS Based Model Screenshot of World Bank Dump Site

Figure 4.4b Align Photos

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Figure 4.4c Build Dense Cloud

Figure 4.4d. Build Mesh

Figure 4.4e Build Texture

Figure 4.4f. Build DEM (Digital Elevation Model)

Build

Figure 4.4g. Ortho-mosaic

Figure 4.4h. Longitudinal Profile Along Dump Site

Figure 4.4i. Volumetric Analysis in Agisoft

Figure 4.4j. Exporting Model as Collada.dae, .pdf, .kml, .obj, .fbx

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Figure 4.4k 3D GIS Based Model Screenshot of World Bank Dump Site Centre view

Figure 4.4l 3D GIS Based Model Screenshot of World Bank Dump Site from middle view

Figure 4.4m. 3D GIS Based Model Screenshot of World Bank Dump end view

Figure 4.4n 3D GIS Based Model Screenshot front Road view

figure 4.4o. 3D GIS Based Model Screenshot of World Bank Dump Site left view

Figure 4.4p. 3D GIS Based Model Screenshot of World Bank Dump Site left side view

Figure 4.4q. 3D GIS Based Model Screenshot of World Bank Dump right view

Figure 4.4r. 3D GIS Based Model Screenshot of World Bank Dump Site right side view

Figure 4.4s 2D Satellite of World Bank dump site

Mapping of the Waste Collection and Disposal Point with Buffer Analysis

Buffering shown in figure 4.5 and table 4.2 is the process of specifying distance around one or more features such as road, rivers, and building areas, this is based on each feature's attribute values. For this project the specified buffer zone was applied on the dump point based on environmental policy standard for ASEPA criteria.

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Figure 4.5 Waste Buffer of Collection at 50, 100m, Disposal at 500, 1000 meters of the study area

Table 4.2a: Digital Database of Sensitive Area 100 Meters

Attributes of Buildings 100 Meters

FID	Shape *	Id	Eastings	Northings	Area
0	Polygon ZM	0	314565.472	562237.115	1.38598
1	Polygon ZM	0	314561.513	562261.065	4.82258
2	Polygon ZM	0	314572.417	562278.502	9.07186
3	Polygon ZM	0	314692.397	566116.678	3.53768
4	Polygon ZM	0	314716.586	566141.801	4.69696
5	Polygon ZM	0	314724.419	566194.464	1.12462
6	Polygon ZM	0	314728.597	562198.559	6.55243
7	Polygon ZM	0	314623.854	562218.23	1.40009
8	Polygon ZM	0	314686.197	562216.928	3.97626
9	Polygon ZM	0	314715.687	562240.059	2.00493
10	Polygon ZM	0	314725.607	562219.532	1.21528
11	Polygon ZM	0	314621.564	562238.681	8.40055
12	Polygon ZM	0	314641.227	562235.845	9.68864
13	Polygon ZM	0	314628.429	562266.452	1.23208
14	Polygon ZM	0	314661.189	562267.831	1.47849
15	Polygon ZM	0	314696.969	562276.14	2.52016
16	Polygon ZM	0	314718.131	562285.225	1.10887
17	Polygon ZM	0	314632.878	562294.345	1.12007
18	Polygon ZM	0	314636.063	562313.787	1.38329
19	Polygon ZM	0	314649.025	562308.743	8.06453
20	Polygon ZM	0	314642.134	562337.864	9.91265
21	Polygon ZM	0	314656.425	562343.347	9.80064
22	Polygon ZM	0	314711.012	562312.28	1.09207
23	Polygon ZM	0	314660.66	562324.064	1.11447
24	Polygon ZM	0	314715.182	562330.385	7.00046
25	Polygon ZM	0	314710.229	562343.974	1.17607
26	Polygon ZM	0	314749.799	562299.38	1.35528
27	Polygon ZM	0	314737.465	562296.116	1.32728
28	Polygon ZM	0	314752.529	562264.093	1.36089
29	Polygon ZM	0	314742.867	562325.974	1.14247
30	Polygon ZM	0	314653.376	563154.118	4.83871
31	Polygon ZM	0	314734.791	563143.591	1.5625
32	Polygon ZM	0	314631.333	563153.155	2.17854
33	Polygon ZM	0	314655.483	563133.305	2.07213
34	Polygon ZM	0	314689.433	563177.749	1.41689
35	Polygon ZM	0	314720.959	563186.826	1.22648
36	Polygon ZM	0	314734.778	563176.394	6.27241
37	Polygon ZM	0	314721.309	563206.927	1.23768
38	Polygon ZM	0	314750.591	563193.908	8.34455
39	Polygon ZM	0	314644.583	563236.603	3.32662
40	Polygon ZM	0	314632.282	563222.798	2.12814

Multi Criteria Analysis

This involved the detailed method of data analysis used in the study area. One of such analysis is multi-criteria analysis done in Arc map 9.2. This combines final hazard layer and final vulnerability layer at 50% each. The resultant layer is the Flood Risk Layer of Aba Urban. That is; Risk = Hazard + Vulnerability. where Hazard surfaces are: Waste collection and dump site, other land use, Slope, Aspect, Relief, and Soil texture and Vulnerability Surfaces are: Population Density, Built-up and Soil-class

The final waste hazard map depicting the above reclassification is presented below

Figure 4.11a Waste Hazard Zonation in Aba

Figure 4.11b Classified Waste Hazard

Table 4.3: Waste Hazard Ranking

Range	Level
63,814,594.68 - 95,721,592	High
31,907,597.34 - 63,814,594.67	Moderate
600 - 31,907,597.33	Low

Vulnerability Surfaces Weight and Zonation

Figure 12: Vulnerability Zonation of the Study Area

Table 4.15 Waste Vulnerability Ranking

Range	Level
5,905.266669 - 8,787.75	High
3,022.783336 - 5,905.266668	Moderate
140.3000031 - 3,022.783335	Low

Table 4.17 Waste Risk Ranking

Range	Level
3,190,763,392 - 4,786,114,560	High
1,595,412,223 - 3,190,763,391	Moderate
61,052.5 - 1,595,412,222	Low

Figure 13: Waste Risk Zonation of the Study Area

Discussion

3D Modelling Analysis Findings and Discussions

From the 3D GIS analysis calculation the Perimeter was 269.252m Area 4633.2 (m²) volume above 47503.9(m³) below 13.659 (m³) total 47490.3 (m³) required to be fill up and bushes cleared as was seen from the Agisoft Metashape Shape Report in the Appendix IV, buildings were close to dump as observed from the model, from oral interview from residence around the area, there are always security threat (armed robbing) from 7.30pm till day break if you are scrolling or trekking along the road as dump hide hoodlum meanwhile it is an illegal disposal site by ASEPA standard.

Buffering Analysis Findings and Discussions

From the buffer analysis 1125 and 7065 buildings housing people around collection and disposal point respectively are living under waste risk. Though, ASEPA laws, policies and regulations ascertained structural characteristics of development observed by the researcher. It was revealed that some infrastructures around dump site wasn't there before the place was use as dump site but development and expansion of the city towards Aba River (Water Side) came along as time goes on. However, the

buffer analysis indicates that human life and other features under are threats of waste pollution, land degradation, marine pollution especially during raining season, this waste are carried into the river by running water because observing the slope and contour of Aba indicate steep slope around the coast especially Emelogu and 7up/Glass dump.

Multi- criteria analysis Findings and Discussions

Hazard

Following the analysis waste hazard surfaces map shown that waste hazard exists in the five LGAs that made up of Aba Metropolis though in different level, the high-level was found in Aba South and along Aba River, the moderate and low were found in all LGAs especially around Osisioma.

Vulnerability

Following the analysis, waste vulnerability surfaces map indicates high waste vulnerability in Aba North and Aba South while the remaining LGAs show moderate and low vulnerability. However, the high vulnerability is as result of high population density in both LGAs especially around CBD

Risk

Following the analysis in the waste risk surfaces map, there are high risk along Aba River and part of Aba South, the moderate and low risk was found Osisioma LGA and other LGAs

Discussions

Waste Hazard will affect road accessibility be seen in the case of Portharcourt road as of the time of data was collection, thus as a business hub of Eastern Nigeria, any road impedance affects business transaction. It will aid in water and air pollution contamination as witness in Aba River (Waterside)

In the area of Waste Vulnerability most Settlement and Population are Vulnerable to waste illegal disposal as observed in Agulanna street where refuse and dump block the road, no accessibility, people

deserted the environment to a better place because the dump was accompanied with flood thus making the environment uninhabitable while a closer street is lively and accessible. General it has an impact on human health especially those living in close radius of the disposal site observe in7up/Glass dump Waste Risk was observed in Secondary Forest and Agricultural loss as Waste creates dangerous greenhouse gases like methane, hydrogen sulphide, and carbon dioxide and traps heat. Temperature increases and causes global warming. Changing climate is unfavourable for the survival of a species that decreases the habitat size. the water can serve as an irrigation source so throughout the year farm product are cultivate and harvest tis was observed in all the dump disposal site. Final there is always risk in Health, and loss of lives and property such experienced around Agulanna primary school and Obunku road. However, waste coupled with flood disaster caused untold hardship on the residents as their sources of livelihood are destroyed. Also, people living along Aba River experienced untold and strange sickness as garbage containing harmful substances are washed down and end-up floating on the river, causing water pollution. Human consumption from polluted water bodies lead to diseases like cholera, diarrhoea and dysentery.

Comparative discussion of three analysis for suitability pattern

Finally, analysing the results findings from the three analyses (the 3D GIS-Based model, the buffer and multi-criteria analysis), field observation, oral interview from resident, collection point should increase at least a walking distance, if possible, house to house collection of refuse, nevertheless, with the analyses and supervise classification indicate that no area within the metropolis is suitability for waste disposal. Therefore, all the three-disposal dumpsite should be close and reclaimed for another purpose as this area are not good for habitant, thus relocating of disposal dump outside the metropolis will be an optimal agenda for a sustainable environment.

5 Conclusion

Based on this research findings, the following conclusion can be drawn: solid waste as a major environmental problem in Aba metropolis was due to few of ASEPA facility to combat the growing population of the city waste, as it was observed that the facility is there year all round while the population and its density increase rapidly. Therefore, waste assessment should involve the integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing Systems technology with appropriate methodology in assessing waste risk as this is a threat to human lives and environment.

6 Recommendation

Solid waste is projected to triple in volume by 2050. If waste in urban area is managed improperly, untreated, and disposed of in open dumps and this will continue to contribute to an increase in greenhouse gas emissions and global and local land and water pollution, which affect the health and welfare of impoverished people disproportionately. Therefore, based on the analysis and findings in the study area in assessing the waste risk, a hazards and vulnerability, the following waste mitigation strategies are recommended.

- i) There should be house to house collection of waste to enable government combat and control the discharge of waste within the urban area, this can be achieved successful with help of database creation in Geographic Information System especially 3D model of waste, buildings, road as this will show reality of Aba and its environment as can be seen with satellite imageries and in the 3D model analysis from drone.
- ii) Construction of drainage wedge at every house corner so that any individual that indiscriminately discharge waste in the drainage system should be punish and this will reduce flood during raining season as experience in Aba around June July during corn roasting and raining season.

- iii) Compliance guidelines outlined by the Abia State Environmental Protection Agency (ASEPA), Ministry of Environment and Town Planning laws, policies and regulation should be reviewed from time to time to suit reformation and expansion of the urban as it was observed that the same ASEPA facility in the collection has served for several years while population and its density keep growing through birth rate and migration to commercial city from neighbouring towns, villages, other state and even outside country as investors come to invest there. Therefore, by reviewing these laws, guidelines and regulations, you'll be assured you are staying on top of any changes and that you'll be accessing the latest tools and resources to ensure compliance especially Remote Sensing and GIS.
- iv) GIS technology and Remote sensing systems should be used in assessing environmental problems and planning of our urban areas as this will enable government to know the land use, geomorphology, landform, soil type, rainfall pattern, slope aspect, contour etc. of each location in the environment.
- v) Waste-auditing is a key way to ensure that all waste facilities are following a proper, storage and disposal protocols. Waste audits from time-to-time help discern how much waste is being generated, identify opportunities to reduce waste and potential cost savings, this can be efficiently with Geospatial technology that can integrate spatial and non- spatial data, for here spatial are location of waste collection and disposal point, non-spatial include the size, population and its density indicating people that make use of waste point

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